

the presence of a buffer-making reagent (this avoided interference due to Al, Cu, and Fe). The intensity of yellow color developed was read at 420 nm on a spectrophotometer.

Three rice hills from each pot were harvested 30 DT. Dry matter was recorded and 1 g samples ashed at 500 °C for 1 h were dissolved in 20 ml of 0.36 NH₂SO₄. A 2-ml aliquot of the solution was analyzed for B following the azomethine-H procedure.

High B concentration at the beginning of both water regimes declined over time. The decrease was faster and steeper in field capacity pots. At 7 DT, the soil solution extracted from the pots at field capacity had about 1.5 times higher B concentration than that extracted from the flooded pots. This trend continued for 2 wk, then reversed (see figure).

Irrespective of water regime, coefficients of correlation ($r = 0.79^{**}$) and the closely parallel changes in water soluble B and EC indicate that B closely follows EC. Coefficients of correlation between water-soluble B and pH, Eh, or r_{CO_2} were not significant.

Dry matter yield of rice in pots maintained at field capacity was about

Periodic changes in EC and concentration of B in soil solution under field capacity and under continuous flooding. Ludhiana, India.

40% less than that of rice in flooded pots (see table). Dry matter yield of continuously flooded rice was higher, and soil solution B at 15-30 DT higher, but uptake of B was lower than in rice grown under field capacity. It appears that aerobic conditions favor higher B uptake by rice than do anaerobic conditions. ■

Dry matter yield and B uptake by 30-d-old rice plants under different soil moisture conditions.

Soil moisture	Dry matter yield (g/pot)	B uptake (µg/pot)
Continuous flooding	13.2	290
Field capacity	8.2	361
S.E. (±)	0.5	10

Variation in temperature of irrigated rice soils with different drainage characteristics

L. C. Dharmasri and B. V. R. Punyawardena, Division of Soil Science, Agriculture Research Centre, Angunukolapellessa, Sri Lanka

Soil temperatures in irrigated ricefields vary with time of day. We measured soil temperature at two positions in the soil catena representing imperfectly drained and poorly drained sandy clay loam soil in an irrigated transplanted ricefield during March 1989.

Soil temperature at 5-cm depth was measured at 1-h intervals from 0700 to 1700 h for five consecutive days during the vegetative growth period, when fertilizer was scheduled to be topdressed. The imperfectly drained field was irrigated once in 4 d; the poorly drained field, once in 6 d. Temperature of the irrigation water ranged from 27.8 to

30.0 °C. Temperature of the standing water ranged from 32.2 to 34.4 °C in imperfectly drained soil and from 30.6 to 32.8 °C in poorly drained soil.

Mean daily soil temperature ranged from 26.7 to 37.5 °C in imperfectly drained soil and 26.4 to 34.7 °C in poorly drained soil (see table). The average maximum soil temperature at 5-cm depth was 35.6 ± 0.4 °C at 1500 h in imper-

fectly drained soil, and 34.1 ± 0.2 °C at 1400 h in poorly drained soil. Soil temperature increased 8.4 °C in 8 h from the nighttime minimum in imperfectly drained soil, and 7.2 °C in 7 h in poorly drained soil.

The widest temperature difference between the two soils was 1.7 °C at 1500 h. Maximum soil temperature could be measured 1400 to 1500 h. ■

Variation in soil temperature of different soil drainage classes. Angunukolapellessa, Sri Lanka.

Time (h)	Imperfectly drained soil		Poorly drained soil	
	Mean daily temperature (°C)	Temperature range (°C)	Mean daily temperature (°C)	Temperature range (°C)
0700	27.2 ± 0.2	26.7 - 28.1	26.9 ± 0.1	26.4 - 21.2
0800	27.4 ± 0.2	26.7 - 28.3	27.2 ± 0.2	26.7 - 27.8
0900	28.2 ± 0.2	27.5 - 28.9	27.7 ± 0.2	27.2 - 28.1
1000	29.4 ± 0.2	28.9 - 29.7	28.7 ± 0.2	28.1 - 29.2
1100	31.1 ± 0.2	30.6 - 31.7	30.2 ± 0.4	29.2 - 31.1
1200	32.9 ± 0.2	32.2 - 33.3	31.8 ± 0.4	30.8 - 33.3
1300	34.4 ± 0.4	33.6 - 36.4	33.1 ± 0.3	32.2 - 33.9
1400	35.4 ± 0.4	34.4 - 36.9	34.1 ± 0.2	33.6 - 34.7
1500	35.6 ± 0.4	35.0 - 37.5	33.9 ± 0.2	33.3 - 34.1
1600	35.1 ± 0.3	34.4 - 36.4	33.7 ± 0.3	32.5 - 34.4
1700	33.9 ± 0.2	33.6 - 34.7	32.9 ± 0.5	31.1 - 33.9